

Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI) & AI for Chemistry: Alchemy

Project: Developing an AI audit tool for data ingestion into the Physical Chemistry
Data Collection
A Joint PSDI & Alchemy Internship 2025 Report
30/06/2025-26/09/2025

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1 Project Details

Project Name	Developing an AI audit tool for data ingestion into the Physical Chemistry Data Collection
Project Dates	30/06/2025-26/09/2025
Website	https://github.com/Maglasch/solvaudit-chat-v3

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1.3 Project Description

The aim of this project was to perform an initial investigation into the the development of an AI-driven data audit tool to streamline the ingestion of datasets into the Physical Chemistry Data Collection. The tool was required to analyse submitted datasets, identify inconsistencies or missing metadata, and propose corrections or canonical mappings to align with chemical standards and support ingestion to the database.

2 Lay Summary

The Solubility Audit Manager (SAM) is a simple, text-based tool that helps researchers clean and organise solubility data so it can be stored consistently in a central database. Researchers often record solubility measurements in different formats, which makes it difficult to compare or combine datasets. SAM solves this by guiding users step-by-step through the process of checking, standardising, and tidying their data.

When a user gives SAM a CSV file, the tool works through a series of stages, producing cleaned versions of the data along with detailed logs that explain what was changed and why. These logs ensure that every step is transparent and easy to trace. The final output is a well-structured CSV file ready for future use in a database. Although SAM currently exports only to CSV, it is designed so that connecting it to a full database system (like MongoDB) would be straightforward in the future.

SAM works through a conversational command-line interface. The user interacts with it by typing natural-language instructions, and SAM uses a built-in AI model to understand these instructions and move through the data-cleaning steps. This makes the process feel more like a guided conversation than a technical task.

3 Introduction

Solubility Audit Manager (SAM) is a command-line Python tool designed to standardise and aid the ingestion of solubility data into a centralised database. The goal of SAM is to take a solubility dataset from existing research in CSV format and guide the user through a step-by-step process to clean, standardise, and curate the data into a consistent schema, producing several intermediate datasets and audit logs for maximum verbosity. The output of SAM is a CSV file as a placeholder for a database, currently the tool does not have the capacity to export the curated database into a database manager e.g MongoDB, but this is a future development that can be implemented with ease. In summary, SAM does the following:

- **Standardises a CSV dataset** into a canonical format with a predefined schema defining rows and columns.
- **Builds intermediate audit datasets** through each stage of the audit process for maximum verbosity and traceability.
- **Outputs artifact files** to be inspected or loaded into the database later, including standardised datasets, validity checks, an audit log, and a transition mapping file.

SAM is an **interactive Command-Line Interface (CLI) application** - when it is run in the Python terminal (e.g using PyCharm), the user engages in a dialogue via text prompt with the tool, utilising a local AI-powered assistant that helps the tool proceed through each of its ingestion states. Inside, SAM uses a local **HuggingFace** large language model (LLM) to interpret user commands or natural-language instructions and decide which tools to invoke and which state the user wishes to be in. The user experience (UX) is designed to be conversational but task-oriented; commands or descriptions are given and SAM responds with confirmations, previews, or suggestions for next-steps.

4 Typical User Workflow

When using SAM, a sequence of steps are followed in an interactive session. Below is an overview of this workflow, illustrating what actions the user takes and how SAM responds at each stage.

1. **Launching SAM:** The user starts the application by running the `sam` command in a python terminal such as PyCharm. On launch, SAM prints a banner with a quick-start guide and presents the core commands of the manager such as `load_data`, `set_schema`, `preview_mapping` etc. An interactive prompt (`sam>`) is shown to indicate to the user that they can interact with the program, and SAM also prints a hint here: *'Paste a CSV path to begin, or type examples'*

2. **Loading a dataset:** The first step is to load a solubility dataset file; the user can simply paste the filepath of the dataset or use the explicit command `load_data <path>`, for example:

```
sam> load_data ./data/solubility_dataset.csv
```

SAM will attempt to open the file. If successful, it reads the file into a pandas DataFrame and resets any previous session state. It then updates the state with dataset details such as name, number of rows/columns, and records the original filepath, producing the message: *"Dataset loaded."*. If this is not possible, an error message is returned instead.

3. **Automatic schema mapping suggestion:** After loading the dataset, SAM proceeds to the intake phase. It runs the `begin_intake` tool which analyses the column headers to guess the mapping of each column to the required schema roles. SAM is designed with an 8-element canonical schema hard-coded in, consisting of:

- solute
- solvent
- solubility value
- solubility unit
- temperature value
- temperature unit
- database
- source

With these 8 headers, SAM uses a list of common keywords associated with each role (e.g. synonyms for "solute" may include *Compound*, *Molecule*, *SMILES* etc.) to populate an initial suggested schema mapping presented to the user.

4. **Reviewing and correcting the schema mapping:** The user is now prompted to examine SAM's suggested role mapping and decide whether to accept or modify it. For the latter condition, the `set_schema` command can be used to specify the mapping explicitly:

```
sam> set_schema solute=<CompoundName>, solvent=<const:water>,
solubility unit = <const:log(mol/L)> ...
```

In this example, the *solute* role is mapped to the column "CompoundName" which will extract the data from this column in the dataset to the DataFrame. Solvent is set using the protected term, "const:" which informs the tool that the value is a literal and not a column name; setting each entry of the DataFrame for this column to the input that proceeds the term, *water*. Roles that should be intentionally left blank (no data) can be assigned to `const:` with a token such as `[None]` or `null` to inform SAM that the role is empty and not to flag it as an issue. The `set_schema` command is flexible; only the roles specified will be changed, any omitted from the manual instruction will keep their previous value from the initial guess or previous update, allowing iterative corrections to the mapping with previews at each stage.

SAM also accepts **natural language instructions** for mappings (to a certain degree of accuracy), allowing the user to interact with the tool by saying: *Use the column SMILES as the solute and 25°C as the temperature.* SAM's parser will interpret the instruction and set the roles appropriately.

5. **Validating the import:** once the mapping is correct, the user proceeds to validation. Typing `—validate_dataset—` or simply `validate`, will perform a series of initial checks and clean-ups to minimise load in the latter stages of curation. During validation, SAM applies the mapping presented in the preview to the entire dataset, creating a new DataFrame with new canonical schema entries. The initial check will **drop rows with missing required fields** (at minimum, `—solute—` and `—solubility value—`) and **remove duplicate entries within the dataset** - by default this is based on having the same combination of `—solute—`, `—solvent—`, and `—solubility value—`, referred to as the "*TRIPLE*".

The result of validation is a cleaned dataset that is ready for assembly into a standardised dataset. SAM will report the output of validation with a message such as: *Validation complete. kept 95, dropped 5, duplicates 2* meaning 95 rows remain, 5 rows were removed (either empty or duplicates), and 2 of those removed were identified as duplicates. It then prompts the user to proceed to the standardisation stage with the prompt message: *"Standardise now? (say 'assemble')"*.

6. **Standardising the submission:** in this stage, the user runs the tool `—assemble_submission—` to produce the standardised output file for the dataset. This command takes the validated dataset, appends four data provenance columns for later use (below), and saves the dataset locally.

- `—_dataset_sha1—` - the **SHA-1** hash of the original file's content
- `—_original_file—` - the original *filename*.
- `—_source_row_1based—` the original row number from the source file
- `—_submission_id—` - a combination of the dataset hash and the row index

SAM writes this dataset to a `—CSV—` file in the `—artifacts/—` directory. The filename is the original dataset's name with `—_standardised.csv—` appended. This stage also duplicates the original input dataset (referred to as the **Bronze** level of the pipeline) into `—artifacts/bronze/—` with a name prefixed by the dataset hash for maximum traceability. Once assembled, SAM prints a message to the user prompting them to proceed to the next stage.

7. **Running the bulk data audit pipeline:** at this point, the user has a standardised dataset for their submission. The next step is to integrate this into the full data audit pipeline via the tool `—run_update_database—` called by "*run backend*" or "*update database*". This operation gathers all of the standardised dataset files in the `—artifacts/—` directory (acting as part of the database, including standardised datasets generated in previous runtimes) and compares them to an existing maintained **Silver** database at `—artifacts/db_silver.csv—`. If this dataset does not already exist, it will be generated. The command to update the database will read the Silver `—CSV—` and append the new rows from the latest standardised file(s). To avoid duplication, it checks for new rows via their `—_submission_id—` to see if they already exist - the result of this is an updated database containing all unique submissions.

Following this, an extensive data audit is performed to check aspects of the imported data. This audit includes:

- Normalisation of the text provided in the solute and solvent fields

- Classifying each solute/solvent as either **InChI**, **Smiles-like**, **Name-like**, or None, by pattern matching
- Converting all temperature units to Kelvin for better deduplication (later)
- Converting solubility to the standard $\log(\text{mol/L})$ form if the given form is mol/L
- If RDKit is available it attempts to generate canonical SMILES for the solute and solvent
- Extracts reference information, parsing DOI or URLs from the `—source—` field using regex
- **Produces an `info_score` for each row, a numeric score indicating information completeness based on the above**

The script then performs **grouping and deduplication**. The data from the Silver dataset is grouped by `—solute_key—`, `—solvent_key—`, and a rounded version of the LogS solubility to three decimals (allowing for a configurable difference between data conversions that may be present between datasets gathered from different sources - `—logS_round0p001—`). This means that all entries that have the same compound and solvent, and essentially the same solubility, will be considered as a group.

For each such group, if the group has multiple entries they will be filtered based on their `—info_score—`, selecting for the highest score (most data-rich entry). The index of the chosen rows are recorded as "alive" and the rest of the rows are marked as "`—drop_triple—`" with detailed notes kept in the audit log. The final collected "alive" rows are returned to the user as the **Gold** database; carrying over the original `—_submission_id—` for each row, as well as returning the normalised/canonicalised solute and solvent names, the solubility value with standardised units ($\log(\text{mol/L})$), temperature in Kelvin, and the original `—database—` and `—source—` fields - this represents the *cleaned, final database*. Lastly, the script builds a translation mapping which links each final row in the Gold database back to all of the original submission rows that contributed it for maximum traceability.

5 Code blocks

The code for SAM consists of 8 python scripts, detailed briefly below. Each of these scripts carries out a particular function, explored further in Appendix ??.

- `—_init_.py—` - Package initializer for SAM (Solubility Audit Manager).
- `—agent.py—` - Chat agent that routes user input to tools (or the LLM).
- `—backend_loader.py—` - Helper script for importing backend python module from a file-path, in this case makes use of `—update_database.py—`.
- `—cli.py—` - Command-line entry point for SAM: parses setup options, prints a quick-start banner, and launches the Read-Eval-Print-Loop (REPL) that wires the LocalHFChat + ChatAgent to backend/intake/update commands.
- `—intake_flow.py—` - Intake+mapping tools including: guess roles, set/preview schema, validate rows, write per-dataset standardised file (with stable IDs), and optionally run the updater.
- `—model_local.py—` - Minimal local HuggingFace LLM wrapper. Builds a chat-style prompt (with tool schema), runs a local HF model, and extracts exactly one JSON action per turn.

- `—mongo_ingest.py—` - **not yet developed!**
- `—state.py—` - State machine for SAM function. Holds current dataset context, accumulated findings, and an optional backend module.
- `—tools_core.py—` - Tool registry and other common tools.
- `—update_database.py—` - Main data audit script that performs checks and deduplication.

6 Example CLI

Listing 1: SAM — Solubility Audit Manager (CLI transcript)

```
(base) solvaudit-chat-v3 % sam
SAM - Solubility Audit Manager
Model (in use): Qwen/Qwen2.5-3B-Instruct

What SAM does:
  1) Standardises your CSV
  2) Builds Silver (verbose) dataset, then a clean Gold dataset (deduped by info
  score)
  3) Writes artifacts you can inspect or load into MongoDB later

Quick start:
  - Paste a CSV path and press Enter
  - I'll guess the column mapping; you can accept or correct it
  - Use constants like const:water, const:'log(mol/L)', const:25, const:C
  - To blank a role (e.g., no source): source=[None]

Core commands:
  load_data <path>
  begin_intake
  set_schema role=col|const:...
  preview_mapping
  validate_dataset
  assemble_submission
  run_update_database

Navigation:
  help    examples    quit

Paste a CSV path to begin, or type examples . (Type quit to exit.)
sam> ./src/combined_meng.csv

Dataset loaded.

Here's my guess at the mapping (edit as needed):
- **solute** -> smiles
- **solvent** -> (not guessed)
- **solubility value** -> logS
- **solubility unit** -> (not guessed)
- **temperature value** -> (not guessed)
- **temperature unit** -> (not guessed)
- **database** -> (not guessed)
- **source** -> (not guessed)
```

```

Preview (first 5 rows across all 8 roles):
<PREVIEW>
Correct the mapping using:
  set_schema solute=<col> solvent=<col|const:water> \
              solubility value=<col> solubility unit=const:'log(mol/L)' \
              temperature value=<col|const:25> temperature unit=<col|const:C>
Or ready to validate? (say 'validate')
sam> set_schema solute=smiles, solvent=const:InChI=1S/H2O/h1H2, solubility value=logS,
       solubility unit=const:log(mol/L), temperature value=const:25, temperature unit=
       const:C

```

```

Applied your mapping.
Here's the current mapping:
- **solute** -> 'smiles'
- **solvent** -> 'InChI=1S/H2O/h1H2'
- **solubility value** -> 'logS'
- **solubility unit** -> 'log(mol/L)'
- **temperature value** -> '25'
- **temperature unit** -> 'C'
- **database** -> 'combined_meng.csv'
- **source** ->

```

```

Preview (first 5 rows across all 8 roles):
<PREVIEW>

```

```

Validate now? (say 'validate')
sam> validate

```

```

Validation OK.
Removed 2455 duplicate row(s) on solute, solvent, solubility value.
Validation complete. kept 125494, dropped 2455, duplicates 2455.
Standardize now? (say 'assemble')
sam> assemble

```

```

Standardised written: artifacts/combined_meng.csv_standardised.csv (rows: 125494)
Standardized written:
'/Users/oscarrobinson/Downloads/solvaudit-chat-v3/artifacts'
Run backend to build Silver/Gold? (say 'run backend')
sam> run backend
Skipped 125494 rows already in Silver (by __submission\_id).

```

```

No new rows to add; curating existing Silver...
Silver: 226465 rows; Gold: 223170 rows.
Backend update finished.
Gold CSV:
'artifacts/db_gold.csv'
Audit CSV:
'artifacts/db_audit.csv'
Translation CSV:
'artifacts/db_translation.csv'
Ingest to Mongo (if configured) or say 'export csv'.
sam> quit

```

7 Conclusion

This summer internship for AIChemistry delivered **SAM**, a chat-based AI-assisted data audit tool that ingests solubility datasets into a simplified, verbose, and deduplicated, placeholder

database (—CSV— file) suitable for the Physical Chemistry Data Collection. The system integrates a CLI with a state-based *bronze* → *silver* → *gold* dataset audit pipeline that completes per-dataset standardisation based on a fixed canonical schema, data provenance via internal identifiers, and normalisation stages to ensure consistency, weighted quantitatively via a configurable —`info_score`— parameter.

Practically, SAM reduces the manual burden of data auditing, providing immediate feedback during intake (schema guessing, previews, validation counts) as a peace-of-mind for the user. By isolating state functions in tools and keeping the interface agent-driven, the system remains modular: new checks or sources can be added without destabilising the user experience.

Limitations of this project include specificity to solubility datasets only, due to the internal tools processing solubility constants, reliance on reasonable header cues for initial schema guesses, and a CSV-first assumption that omits multi-table submissions and potentially richer metadata (e.g., pH, pressure). Furthermore, due to the limited power of the LLM it has been isolated to a purely state-controller use instead of an upfront chatbot.

Future works should focus on developing —`mongo_ingest.py`— to allow for importing to a MongoDB, as well as expanding the data import section to accommodate a wider variety of inputs. An improved version should also account for a broader canonical schema coverage from the original 8 key fields, ensuring that if other metadata is available then it can be stored and retrieved appropriately. Lastly, a further improvement should explore the possibility of using a more powerful LLM, potentially via online hosting, to enable more semantic driven imports (moving away from the inconsistencies of the natural language parsing) and more powerful dataset inference.

8 Outputs, Data & Software Links

The code generated for this project has been made available via this GitHub Repository: <https://github.com/Maglasch/solvaudit-chat-v3>